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The 2025 WHO Pandemic Agreement: Ambitious Goals, Uncertain Future

Issue/Problem

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed significant global inequities in access to vaccines, diagnostics, and treatments. High-income countries secured early supplies, while many low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) [faced significant delays and shortages](#).

Description of the Problem

These disparities revealed deep structural flaws in the global response. Wealthier nations prioritized building [national stockpiles](#), while the [pharmaceutical industry's profit-driven model](#) further limited access for less-resourced countries. Moreover, although many countries contributed critical pathogen samples and data, [they often saw little return](#) in terms of access to resulting medical tools. This imbalance undermined trust, discouraged future cooperation, and weakened pandemic preparedness.

Results

In May 2025, [following three years of negotiation](#), World Health Organization (WHO) member states adopted the [Pandemic Agreement](#). A key feature is the proposed Pathogen Access and Benefit-Sharing (PABS) system, which requires countries to share pathogen samples and sequence data. In exchange, participating manufacturers must reserve 20% of their pandemic-related production for WHO distribution: half as donations and half at reduced prices. The agreement also includes provisions encouraging countries to share technical expertise and intellectual property to expand production capacity in LMICs. However, WHO member states have not yet finalized the PABS annex, which is [essential to putting the agreement into effect](#). Until it is completed, the treaty cannot be opened for signature. It will only enter into force [once 60 countries ratify it](#), a step unlikely to occur [before 2029](#).

Lessons Learned

Past initiatives like the COVID-19 Vaccines Global Access (COVAX) facility failed largely due to [vague commitments](#) and [overreliance on voluntary cooperation](#). Although the Pandemic Agreement [sets more specific and structured targets](#) than previous efforts, key provisions, such as the 20% product allocation, still depend on non-binding contracts with manufacturers. Without enforceable obligations and robust accountability mechanisms, [experts warn](#) that the agreement may fall short of ensuring equitable access in future pandemics.